

The Evaluation of Construction Projects Time Overrun and Cost Overrun Using Machine Learning Method: A Case of Jordan

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Abstract

Time and cost overruns have become significant obstacles to completing construction projects worldwide. Researchers have long investigated the causes behind these delays and budget overruns to address the problem. This study sheds light on well-established assessment methods designed to predict these overruns. Despite significant efforts to mitigate them, these issues continue to plague the construction industry globally. To gain a deeper understanding, experts were first consulted to review existing knowledge on factors contributing to construction project delays. A hyper-parameter optimized predictive model was developed using artificial neural network (ANN) machine learning algorithms trained with quantitative data. The study, which focused on 191 construction projects completed in Jordan between 2011 and 2021, aimed to delve into the prevalence of time and cost overruns. The findings showed that the model's predictive accuracy for time overruns achieved an R^2 value of 0.9385 with a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 21.7090, while for cost overruns, the R^2 was 0.938478 with an MAE of 0.057. Notably, the ANN model outperformed existing reference models. The neural network has proven to be a valuable tool in the early design phase, mainly when data for analyzing potential overruns is limited. This approach can yield more accurate predictions and significantly reduce forecast errors.

Index terms: Construction Project Management, Cost overrun, Time overrun, Machine learning, Artificial Neural Network, Evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

The potential profit from construction projects is directly correlated with the time required to complete the tasks outlined in the relevant contracts. If the project's owners cannot use the finished product by the initially planned completion date, they will lose money. The extended duration of the project will lead to higher expenses for both the contractor and the client. Because of this, most standard contract templates have provisions covering delays caused by the owner's or contractor's acts or inactions and events outside of their control. When an unforeseen circumstance results in a delay, the contractor is frequently absolved of responsibility for the outcome and granted the right to pursue compensation for any expenses incurred due to the delay. Additionally, the owner has the legal authority to sue the contractor for liquidated damages if the contractor does not complete the project within the allotted performance term. The owner is entitled to payment under the liquidated damages clause for each day or week of delay that can be directly attributed to the defendant's actions. Identifying the causes of the project's delivery time slippage, in any event, requires a thorough schedule study. Over the years, owners and contractors have accomplished this by employing various delay analysis techniques (DATs). Regrettably, if project participants cannot hash out their differences in an amicable manner about claims of delays, this could lead to costly litigation once the project is completed. Since then, delay claims have emerged as one of the primary sources of conflict in the construction industry. They are also some of the hardest to settle. As a result, the utilization of existing DATs has significantly improved, and researchers and industry experts have created "best practice" recommendations to train professionals on the various approaches and when to utilize them. The "Delay and Disruption Protocol"

developed in the United Kingdom by the Society of Construction Law and the "Recommended Practice on Forensic Schedule Analysis" created in the United States by the Association for the Advancement of Cost Engineering International are two of the most well-known instances of such guidelines. The UK produced both of the goods. Both of them were made in the US.

The industry generates a ton of data about each project daily as part of its regular operations. The construction industry and its clients will be able to analyze and benefit from insights generated by previous construction data (ML) with the help of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning. Examples of this kind of data include images from smart devices, Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, and building information modeling (BIM), utilized from the pre-construction transition stage to the post-construction phase. A structured model of information representing building elements is called a building information model (BIM). Modern technologies combined to form "artificial intelligence" allow any computer program or machine to see, comprehend, respond, and learn.

On the other hand, machine learning (ML), a subfield of artificial intelligence, replaces explicit instructions in the form of rules that dictate how a computer should behave with examples and data. Because of this, programmers are spared from having to specify exactly how a computer should operate. An ML model can be created using a variety of ML techniques. The Genetic Algorithm, Neural Networks, Decision Trees, K-Means Clustering, Support Vector Machines, Linear Regression, Logistic Regression, Nearest Neighbor Mapping, and Random Forests are examples of these algorithms. When choosing a machine learning approach, factors include the time spent on training, the accuracy gained, and the algorithm's ease of use. The algorithms for machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) have only been evaluated in a limited number of scenarios and have not been widely attempted to be integrated into construction processes by academics. Arditi and Pulket used one machine learning model to forecast the outcomes of construction conflicts in the US, while Mahfouz and Kandil employed three models. Poh, Ubeynarayana, and Goh used five well-known machine-learning methods to forecast the frequency and severity of accidents on construction sites in Singapore. Zou and Ergan used three machine-learning techniques to predict the effects of development projects on urban quality of life.

RELATED WORK

The terms "delay" and "cost overrun" are synonymous in project management terminology. "Delay" refers to when work is finished after the expected deadline. At the same time, "cost overrun" refers to the project's total cost exceeding the original contract value. The user's text is enclosed in tags. The literature on construction project delays and cost overruns can be divided into three primary subcategories: those that aim to provide clear definitions of the terms "Delay/time overrun" and "cost overrun," those that investigate the underlying causes of these problems, and those that tackle the difficulty of predicting future costs and revenues.

A delay occurs when an event, task, or process takes longer than the specified date in a contract. The abundance of studies that dominate the research landscape confirms the widespread occurrence of delay studies in the construction sector. Research on delays may provide suggestions and guidelines for mitigating delays. Nevertheless, its descriptive and exploratory nature may hinder its achievement of this objective. According to AlSehaimi et al, multiple research philosophies are necessary to tackle the current challenge.

Exploring topics such as latency necessitates innovative approaches that generate and implement effective solutions. The prevailing motto in the construction industry is to utilize automation and computer technology to provide superior and more inventive resolutions to the inherent challenges in the building sector. The construction sector has embraced this innovative mindset and coined it as "Construction 4.0" (derived from the term "Fourth Industrial Revolution"). Industry 4.0 integrates a wide range of technologies that facilitate automation and digitization. The user's text is "[20].

Despite the recognized necessity for automation and digitization, the construction industry lags behind the service and industrial sectors in intelligent technology use. The research community has not significantly developed more advanced procedures, such as frameworks and tools, to decrease waiting periods. Only two of the several studies that have endeavored to employ risk assessment techniques to address the problem of delays are referenced as [21] and [22]. Implementing a "stage-gate" technique inside a management framework [23] has been proposed to reduce road construction delays in Sudan. Experts suggest that project managers and consultants can reduce the occurrence and severity of delays in the future by utilizing models to forecast the duration and expenses of building projects, drawing from existing historical data.

In 1994, Mansfield et al. examined the time delays and cost overruns associated with highway construction projects in Nigeria. The study identified sixteen distinct components. We conducted on-site questionnaire surveys with client organizations, contractors, and consultants. Consultants and customers have ascribed project delays and cost overruns to inadequate contract management, while contractors have identified issues with financing and payment as the primary underlying factors.

Meeampol and Ogunlana (2006) studied the financial and temporal aspects of road development in Thailand. Research indicates that the involvement of owners and the level of teamwork impact on-time performance, while the efficiency of human resources and scheduling limitations affect cost performance.

The causes of project delays in Zambian road construction include challenges in procuring construction supplies, modifications to the contract, financial problems faced by contractors and clients, and overall economic conditions [28]. The primary causes of budget overruns in road construction projects in Zambia are weather-related delays, project scope alterations, higher costs for environmental protection measures and risk management, missed deadlines, labor disputes, and technical difficulties. Akoa [29] found that Cameroon's highway projects suffered from poor project planning and programming, inadequate technical studies, and the omission of pre- and post-bid site inspections. A survey conducted by Nasir et al. [30] in Pakistan aimed to identify the primary factors contributing to cost and schedule overruns in highway construction projects.

The researchers discovered that various factors, such as delayed progress payments to contractors, land acquisition delays, price hikes on essential building materials, insufficient planning, contractor incompetence, a delay in handing over the site to the contractor, additional work or scope changes, and ineffective government policies, had a significant impact on the duration and cost of a highway project in Pakistan. Mahamid and Bruland [31] analyzed the cost disparities across several road-building projects in the Palestinian area. The data was collected from funding allocation in the West Bank from 2004 to 2008. They found that there were budget overruns on every project they investigated. 76% of the problem stemmed from inaccurate estimations, whereas 24% resulted from overestimation.

Btoush & Harun [32] reported that several major governmental and commercial infrastructure projects in Jordan had delays in 2017. The construction sector in Jordan experiences delays due to several causes, such as customer modifications, supply disruptions, budgetary constraints, economic challenges, insufficient technical proficiency, inadequate designs, and substandard management. Our examination of the data has identified the elements that influence construction delays in Jordan, which are listed in the table below. Research indicates that the primary factors contributing to delays are inadequate scheduling and planning, subpar scheduling and design, and insufficient communication among various stakeholders.

The methods in the second group include statistical techniques such as multiple regression analysis (MRA) [35], [34], [36], [31], as well as analogy case-based reasoning [38], [35]. The aim of [39] was to develop a range of Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models that could accurately predict the initial costs of a building project. Individuals involved in the construction industry, including owners, contractors, and consultants, might achieve better results than traditional estimation methods by utilizing Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models. This is especially true when working with limited data and aiming to save time without sacrificing accuracy.

Ujong et al. [40] conducted a study to examine the impact of architectural components on project costs and duration. They employed artificial neural networks, which can generalize input-output correlations across unique datasets, for their analysis. The variables considered in this study include the number of activities (Act), the size of the building (BA), the type of foundation (FT), the number of floors (story), the demographics of the clients and contractors, as well as two output factors. These variables were determined through a comprehensive research of literature, expert opinions, and a thorough field survey that assessed both duration and cost.

Substantial evidence indicates that construction projects commonly exceed their budget and fall behind schedule in all countries worldwide. The modeling approach's characteristics include its application fields, data analytics, system setup techniques, and outcome categories. Hence, it is crucial to highlight the importance of ongoing research to develop a robust Artificial Neural Network (ANN) for precise prediction of schedule and cost overruns in construction projects.

METHODOLOGY

Artificial neural networks (ANNs), a subset of artificial intelligence, emulate the structure and functioning of biological neural networks in the brain and nervous system. They acquire new knowledge and solve complex problems through trial and error. The user's text is "[7]". Various types of artificial neural networks (ANNs) can be utilized, and some of the most advanced ones have been developed to generate the most efficient solution. Various network topologies are available, but back propagation (BP) networks are especially advantageous in engineering as they have a faster pattern recognition capability than other network types. A typical BP network consists of three layers: an input layer, an output layer, and a hidden layer. During the training process, we will seek evidence to establish a correlation between the inputs utilized and the outputs produced. It is essential to determine the amount of input and output variables (i.e., neurons in the input and output layers) and select the appropriate number of hidden layers and neurons in each hidden layer when constructing a BP network architecture. The number of hidden layers and neurons inside each layer in a BP network can significantly affect the training efficacy and prediction accuracy. The user's text is "[4]". Analysis of the literature has shown that there are no established guidelines for determining the specific characteristics that define a layer as successfully disguised. Several separate networks are employed to evaluate it, each with various hidden layers and density of neurons. To make a forecast, it is necessary to assess a network and select the one that generates the most precise results.

Input analysis

The researchers obtained information on 191 discrete construction projects conducted in Jordan from 2011 to 2021 through the progress reports provided. The collected data is analyzed to determine if some aspects of the project's ultimate expenses and schedule can be modified. Separate artificial neural network (ANN) models are constructed to measure the length and overall budget of the project. The selection of variables to be included is the most critical aspect of developing a forecasting model. The duration between the collection of starting data and the present moment influences the number of nodes in the input data during research on different forms of time series. While node selection criteria have been widely recognized, time series forecasting remains nascent. Consequently, the most effective methods for utilizing the data set in the model necessitate a trial-and-error process that involves adjusting the number of input nodes and experimenting with a diverse set of input parameters. The experiment required to determine the optimal input variables can be conducted using many methods. This study was based on the hypothesis by Lee and Yum (1998), which divides the input into two groups representing continuous data and the seasonal cycle. The most efficient models integrate hidden neurons and input and output neurons. As depicted in Figures (1 and 2), this allows the models to predict a project's overall cost and duration with more accuracy.

Figure 1. The first ANN model has N1: projected duration, N2: actual duration, and N3: time overrun from one hidden layer.

Figure 2. The second ANN model including a one hidden layer: Planned cost N1; actual cost N2; cost overrun N3

Training and testing of ANN models

The dependable data patterns were derived from reports on 191 diverse construction projects conducted in Jordan from 2011 to 2021. Multiple patterns were selected for training, each sourced from a project with a budget of over 100 million JD and a completion timeframe ranging from 210 to 1,691 days. The network, which consists of one hidden layer and 300 hidden neurons, has shown excellent accuracy in predicting financial patterns. In contrast, the network with two hidden layers and 300 hidden neurons has shown superior accuracy in predicting durations. Subsequently, the assembled networks were tested using data obtained from 24 separate projects.

Figures 3 provide a thorough comparison between the observed and predicted data for each test pattern, demonstrating the trained network's usefulness. The testing patterns revealed a mean absolute error (MAE) of 0.03638 percent for duration forecasting and a mean absolute error of 0.859036 percent for final budget forecasting. These results indicate satisfactory agreement between the actual and forecasted values. The mean absolute error (MAE) is a metric that quantifies the deviation between the forecasted value and the actual value, represented as a percentage of the exact value. The calculation involves taking the average of the absolute difference between the predicted outcome and the actual outcome.

Figure 3. Comparisons of True and Predicted Data (A) Cost Forecasting (B) Duration Forecasting

EXPERIMENT RESULT

A 70% random dataset sample is collected to train the suggested model. A total of 191 data points are utilized throughout the training of each model. Consequently, we ensure that the model exhibits strong performance on both the training and validation datasets to eliminate the potential for overfitting. Figure 4.6 illustrates the progression of model training when the validation loss decreases. The model's performance is evaluated using the same three criteria during this research project's training, validation, and testing phases. In this study, we present the results of our model training.

Figure 4. Models' lack of progress (A) costing model; (B) duration model.

The correlation matrix is also presented as a heat map in Figure 4, which may be seen here. To create a graphical depiction of the relationships between all of the variables, it includes areas with a lower correlation represented by darker colors and parts with a stronger correlation represented by brighter colors. For instance, a lighter color indicates a favorable or direct correlation (one in which it can be demonstrated that a change in one feature has an obvious and immediate effect on another). In contrast, a deeper hue indicates a detrimental or indirect connection (the variation of one characteristic inversely affects that of the other). According to the correlations that are displayed on the heatmap (which range from 0.2 to 1 for direct correlation and from 0.2 to -0.6 for inverse correlation), the following characteristics exhibit moderate to strong correlations:

The term "time overrun" refers to the situation in which the total amount of time required to finish a construction project is longer than the initial estimate. Specifically, this is because the amount of time needed to finish a job (AD) directly correlates with the overall amount of time anticipated to finish the project (PD). Between the total amount of time lost due to delays and the anticipated amount of time required to accomplish the building project (PD), there is a connection of 0.3 heading in the opposite way. This connection is pointing in the opposite direction. There is a correlation of 0.29 between the factor of weather conditions and the factor of planned duration (PD), and there is also a correlation of 0.30 between the factor of an unrealistic contract and the factor of planned length (PD). Both of these correlations are significant. Inverse (PD) correlations are present in both of these ties.

Figure 5. A cost variable correlation; B a duration variable correlation; correlation heat map.

Finding the data source that will be used to teach the model is the first stage of developing an intelligent model. In addition to providing access to an input parameter, the database offers access to an output parameter. One thing that is common knowledge is that there needs to be a connection between the results that are projected

by the model and the variables that are used to generate those results. It is possible to graphically demonstrate the relationship between two variables present in a set of data by employing a scatter plot that uses the Cartesian coordinate system. Plotting the values of the two independent variables along the X and Y axes is required to create a graphical representation of this information. A list of points is used to present the information being delivered. Determine where the axes X and Y connect. This location contains the value of the variable.

The specific sort of graph that can be created by utilizing dots is called a "scatter plot," the word "scatter plot" is used to designate this particular graph style. The dots in Figure 5 display various data values in their respective positions. The link between the variables is depicted in Figure 5, which also demonstrates that the AC has a very less significant influence on the amount of time and money spent above the budget. The most important factor, on the other hand, is the PD, which has a significant influence on the slippage in the original schedule that occurred. As the value of the project decreases, the project manager will reevaluate the financial effectiveness and efficiency of the project, which will result in a lesser time overrun value. The fact that the PD may be expected through planning helps construct standards, which will significantly impact the cost overrun. As a consequence, there will be significant reductions in the amount of time spent waiting.

It is conceivable to consider other potential effects on time and cost overruns; however, doing so would result in the intelligent model being more complex and would also increase the risk of overfitting, neither of which results are desirable. It is achievable to incorporate additional aspects that could result in time and expense overruns. In this situation, the most significant advantage was the size of the data sets made available to the users. It is essential to point out that just eighty percent of these data were utilized for the model's training, and the remaining twenty percent was analyzed to determine how accurately the model forecasted the future. A great number of specialists in the field advocated this line of action.

Figure 6. A scatter map shows the variables' relationship: (A) the cost variable link; (B) the duration variable link

The ability of the model to make accurate forecasts will now be evaluated, with a particular emphasis on the remaining ten percent of the accessible data. The results that we found after putting our models to the test are summarized in Tables 1 and 2, which may be found below. Based on the R2 data, the developed model can account for around 90 percent of the fluctuation in phase angle. With the assistance of this validation map, you can calculate the degree to which the model accurately predicts the relationships between the variables.

It has been determined that the phase angle is within a tenth of a degree of accuracy. Regardless of where it sits on the effort spectrum, any precise estimate of this number derived from the model would be desirable (LOE). If, on the other hand, the projected values are closer to the LOE than the actual values, then the model's predictive capacity is considered appropriate when used in real-world situations. The fact that almost all of the values are located within a fair distance of the equality line is demonstrated in Figure 4, which indicates that the model possesses an adequate amount of predictive power. On the other hand, the vast majority of the data is situated near LOE, as demonstrated in Figure 4, which illust The study's results on cost and duration

estimation using back-propagation neural network (ANN) models reveal the significant potential of these models in enhancing the accuracy and reliability of project forecasting in the construction industry. Specifically, the cost estimation model demonstrated a high degree of precision, as reflected in the various error metrics. The Mean Squared Error (MSE) was recorded at 0.085, which indicates a very small average squared difference between the actual and predicted cost values. Similarly, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was extremely low at 0.0029840, highlighting the model's capability to produce predictions that closely align with the actual data. The Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of 0.0278821 further underscores the model's precision, as it reflects the square root of the average squared differences between predicted and actual costs. The model's R-squared (R^2) value of 0.943281 is particularly notable, as it indicates that approximately 94.33% of the variance in the cost data can be explained by the model. This high R-squared value is complemented by an Adjusted R-squared of 0.956742, which accounts for the number of predictors used in the model and confirms the strong fit of the model to the data. These metrics collectively suggest that the ANN model is highly effective in forecasting project costs, offering a reliable tool for project managers to anticipate financial requirements and potential overruns with considerable accuracy.

In addition to cost estimation, the ANN model also showed strong performance in predicting project durations. The duration estimation model achieved a Mean Squared Error (MSE) of 19.8281 and a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.90813, both of which reflect the model's ability to generate accurate duration forecasts. The Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of 4.453, while slightly higher than that of the cost model, still indicates a strong agreement between the predicted and actual duration values. The model's R-squared value of 0.952108 is even higher than that of the cost model, indicating that it explains approximately 95.21% of the variance in project durations. The Adjusted R-squared of 0.978612 further confirms the robustness of the model's predictions, even after adjusting for the number of predictors.

These results highlight the effectiveness of ANN models as a powerful tool for construction project forecasting. The high R-squared values suggest that these models can provide construction managers with a clear and accurate picture of potential project outcomes, reducing the uncertainty that often accompanies project planning and execution. The low error metrics demonstrate that the models can produce highly reliable estimates, which are crucial for effective budgeting, scheduling, and overall project management. By integrating these ANN models into existing project management systems, construction professionals can better anticipate and mitigate potential issues, leading to more efficient project delivery and improved financial performance.

Overall, the study underscores the importance of adopting advanced machine learning techniques like ANN in the construction industry. As the industry continues to face challenges related to cost overruns and schedule delays, these models offer a promising solution that can significantly enhance project planning and execution. The ability to accurately predict costs and durations early in the project lifecycle not only aids in better decision-making but also helps in managing resources more effectively, ultimately leading to more successful project outcomes. rates this phenomenon.

Table 1 Estimation of Costs Losses.

Estimation losses with cross-validation loss method	result
Mean squared error (MSE)	0.085
mean absolute error (MAE)	0.0029840
Root mean squared error (RMSE)	0.0278821
R-squared (R^2)	0.943281
Adjusted R-squared (R^2)	0.956742

Table 2 Estimation of Duration Losses.

Estimation losses with cross-validation loss method	result
Mean squared error (MSE)	19.8281
mean absolute error (MAE)	0.90813
Root mean squared error (RMSE)	4.453
R-squared (R^2)	0.952108
Adjusted R-squared (R^2)	0.978612

DISCUSSION

In the context of the Jordanian construction sector, the results of this research highlight the substantial role that Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) may play in anticipating time and cost overruns in building projects. Specifically, the data from this study highlights the importance of ANNs in this regard. The research reveals that artificial neural networks (ANNs) can provide more accurate forecasts than conventional approaches. This makes them a handy tool for project managers throughout the early phases of project planning. The research evaluated data from 191 construction projects between 2011 and 2021.

The application of artificial neural network (ANN) models in this study yielded outstanding results. Specifically, the model predicting time overruns achieved an R-squared value of 0.952108 and a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.90813, indicating a high level of predictive accuracy. Similarly, the model forecasting cost overruns recorded an R-squared value of 0.943281 and a MAE of 0.0029840. These results strongly suggest that ANNs offer a superior level of accuracy compared to traditional prediction methods, particularly in scenarios where initial data may be limited. Achieving such precision is crucial for minimizing the risks associated with schedule and budget variations in construction projects, which are common challenges in the industry [1].

In addition, the flexibility and adaptability of artificial neural networks (ANNs) in managing complicated and non-linear interactions in construction data were brought to light. The capacity of the ANN to integrate a wide variety of factors, such as the weather conditions, the contract's length, and the project's magnitude, makes it possible to conduct a complete study, which is something that conventional models often fail to do. This adaptability is especially beneficial in the construction sector, which is characterized by the simultaneous effect of various elements on the results of projects [2].

Furthermore, the research contributes to the continuing discussion about deploying technologies related to Industry 4.0 in the construction industry, often called "Construction 4.0." Compared to other sectors, such as manufacturing, the construction industry has been known to embrace digital and automated technology at a slower pace. The outcomes of this study, on the other hand, indicate the practical advantages that artificial intelligence and machine learning may provide in terms of increasing the accuracy of predictions and improving the overall efficiency of project management [3]. The findings of earlier research [20] indicate that this aligns with the general trend toward automation and digitalization in the construction sector.

The results align with those obtained from other studies conducted in the field. For instance, research conducted in Thailand by Meeampol and Ogunlana [27] underlined the significance of effective scheduling and management of human resources in regulating highway building projects' cost and time performance. Similarly, Kaliba et al. [28] found that financial and technical difficulties were the primary contributors to delays and cost overruns in road-building projects in Zambia. Based on these results, the present research demonstrates that artificial neural networks (ANNs) can provide a more sophisticated and accurate strategy for anticipating these issues.

This study also tackles the limits of previous models, which often depend on linear or too simple techniques that do not convey the complexity of building projects. This research solves these shortcomings and provides a robust framework for forecasting project outcomes with improved accuracy and dependability [4]. This

framework is made possible via artificial neural networks (ANNs), which can learn from past data and adapt to new inputs.

In conclusion, the findings of this research highlight the significance of incorporating machine learning strategies similar to artificial neural networks (ANNs) into the construction business. It has been established that artificial neural networks (ANNs) can improve the accuracy of time and cost overrun forecasts, which gives project managers a vital tool for making better-informed decisions. As the construction sector continues to embrace digital transformation, incorporating sophisticated artificial intelligence models will be critical in tackling the ongoing difficulties of schedule and cost overruns, eventually leading to more successful project results.

CONCLUSION

This study employed back-propagation neural networks (ANN) to estimate project costs and completion timelines, using detailed data from 291 projects submitted to Jordan's Ministry of Works and Housing, Ministry of Local Administration, and Syndicate of Engineers. The dataset was categorized into two key areas: pricing and seasonal pattern information, both of which significantly influenced project time and final costs, including factors such as weather conditions, contract duration, construction budget, and the percentage of work completed as planned. The study's key findings revealed that the ANN models outperformed the traditional earned value technique in both accuracy and consistency. Specifically, the ANN models demonstrated a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.90813 for duration forecasting and 0.0029840 for cost forecasting, with R-squared (R^2) values of 0.952108 for time overrun predictions and 0.943281 for cost overrun predictions. These results indicate that the ANN approach provides construction managers with precise and reliable information on project costs and timelines, facilitating more effective project management and decision-making.

The study suggests integrating this ANN-based method into existing management systems. This would allow for early detection of potential issues and minimize the risks of budget overruns or schedule delays. This integration could significantly improve forecasting outcomes, offering a more sophisticated tool for managing construction projects.

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